

Integrated Technology for Carcinoma Detection

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ABSTRACT

Globally, cancer ranks as the second most common cause of death. Around 10 million people worldwide will lose their lives to cancer in 2020, according to a World Health Organization (WHO) assessment. The most prevalent gynecological cancer among Indian women is ovarian cancer. Every typical woman has two ovaries, one on each side of the uterus. Ovaries are a component of the female reproductive system. Due to the lack of appropriate signs for detection, the risk of ovarian cancer increases starting at age 35 and peaks between the ages of 55 and 64. With a 45% 5-year survival rate, it has the poorest prognosis of any gynecological malignancy. Effective therapy and halting the spread of cancer cells to other body areas depend heavily on early identification of ovarian cancer. Two recent technical developments in early cancer diagnosis are artificial intelligence (AI) and nanotechnology. Using nanoparticles to apply nanoscience to medicine is known as nanotechnology. AI is also useful in nanomedicine design since it optimizes material qualities. High standards of health care management must be attained by making prompt judgments based on informatics analysis, intelligent data analysis, and quick diagnostics in order to deliver higher-quality healthcare in early diagnoses. Here, we examine and highlight artificial intelligence techniques based on nanotechnology.

1. Introduction

Postmenopausal women are most commonly affected by ovarian cancer (OC), which manifests as bloating and abdominal pain several months before it is discovered. Since the early stages of the disease are frequently asymptomatic, most individuals receive their diagnosis at an advanced stage. OC is the seventh most frequent cancer in women globally, accounting for over 314,000 new cases (3.4% of all new cancer cases in females) every year, according to Global Cancer Statistics 2020. The stage of diagnosis has a substantial impact on the prognosis; survival rates for stages I, II, III, and IV are 73–92%, 45–55%, 21%, and less than 6%, respectively. This highlights the need for improved early identification of ovarian cancer. Although the epidemiological statistics of the four primary forms of ovarian cancer—epithelial, germ cell, sex chord, and stromal—vary, epithelial ovarian cancer (EOC) accounts for around 90% of all instances.

The science and technology of diagnosing, treating, and preventing illnesses is known as nanomedicine. Through the use of nanoscale chemicals, biotechnology, genetic engineering, intricate mechanical systems, and nanorobots, it is also utilized to control pain and protect and enhance human health. Compared to human cells, nanoscale devices are a thousand times smaller. Drug administration, gene therapy, monitoring and diagnostics, medication transportation, biomarker tracing, medications, and histopathological imaging are just a few of the promising results that nanotechnology has produced in the treatment of cancer. Gold nanoparticles and quantum dots (QDs) are used at the molecular level to diagnose cancer. Tumors may be accurately and rapidly diagnosed using molecular diagnostic methods based on these nanoparticles, such as biomarker discovery.

A subfield of computer science called artificial intelligence studies machines that carry out tasks that call for human intelligence. One kind of artificial intelligence called machine learning uses

massive datasets of prior examples to train an algorithm. It is used to identify trends, categorize information, or choose the best course of action for ovarian cancer. Medical imaging and gene expression pattern analysis are two areas of medicine that have made use of machine learning and artificial intelligence in general.

In the fight against cancer, early detection is half the problem solved. Imaging methods commonly used to diagnose cancer include X-rays, PET scans, CT, magnetic resonance imaging, and ultrasonography. The final confirmation of cancer is aided by morphological changes in tissues or cells (histopathology or cytology). Cancer may have spread and resulted in metastases by the time these methods identify it, which occurs only after noticeable alterations in tissues have occurred. The inability of traditional imaging methods to differentiate between benign and malignant tumors is another drawback. Furthermore, histopathology and cytology cannot be used as sensitive, stand-alone assays to identify cancer early. Nanotechnology provides a more rapid and precise initial diagnosis as well as a continuous evaluation of cancer patient treatment through the use of novel molecular contrast fluids and materials. **The availability of several nanomaterials and artificial intelligence methods for early ovarian cancer diagnosis are thoroughly described in this review. When combined with nanotechnology, artificial intelligence (AI) demonstrates new and innovative technological aspects in the early detection of carcinoma in females, which can lower the death rate in the female population.**

2. Nano materials and AI in ovarian cancer detection

2.1 Nano materials in ovarian cancer detection

One of the elements to be taken into account for successful cancer treatment is early cancer identification. As technology has advanced, newer methods for detecting cancer have been employed, such as optical-based imaging. Cancer imaging has improved thanks to the application of nanoparticles for image contrast and enhancement. The following list of nanoparticles includes some that have shown promise as cancer detection methods.

Diagnostic techniques based on nanotechnology are being developed as promising instruments for the

quick, easy, and economical diagnosis and detection of cancer. This article discusses the use of nanotechnology in cancer diagnostics and provides an overview of recent advancements in the field. Indicating the presence of cancer in the body, a cancer biomarker is a detectable biological molecule present in blood and other bodily fluids, including urine and saliva. Utilizing nanotechnology to identify extracellular cancer biomarkers

Figure 1: Types of Nano materials

Indicating the presence of cancer in the body, a cancer biomarker is a detectable biological molecule present in blood and other bodily fluids, including urine and saliva. When cancer is present, the body or cancer cells may release proteins (secreted proteins or cell surface proteins), carbohydrates, or nucleic acids (circulating tumor DNA, miRNA, etc.) as cancer biomarkers. Measuring specific amounts of cancer biomarkers helps track the effectiveness of treatment and allows for early detection of cancer or tumor recurrence. High sensitivity and selectivity as well as the capacity to assess several targets at once are provided by nanotechnology. Nanoparticles or nanomaterials can be used to enhance biosensors to enable precise targeting.

Furthermore, using nanoparticles increases the surface-to-volume ratio, which improves the sensitivity of biosensors in meeting the requirements of particular biomolecular diagnostics. Three popular nanoparticle probes for cancer diagnosis are polymer dots (PDs), gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), and quantum dots (QDs). When compared to macroscopic materials, nanomaterials have a number of unique chemical and physical characteristics. There are two main types for nanoparticles. Particles that are primarily composed of organic molecules, while the second type often consists of minerals and metals

Figure 2: Nano Particles

2.1.2 Organic nanoparticles:

2.1.2.1 Liposomes

Liposomes are used as drug delivery systems in chemotherapy for a variety of human malignancies, including breast cancer. Liposomes are cave-sphere-shaped vesicles that contain both hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. Because liposomes may encapsulate hydrophilic molecules within their aqueous core and hydrophobic molecules within their lamellae, they can be regarded as an excellent drug carrier.

2.1.2.2 Dendrimers

Dendrimers are used as contrast agents in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and aid in the detection of various disease conditions. Large, spherical molecules called dendrimers form radial bonds from a central focus point. Commonly branching molecules, dendrimers are composed of natural or artificial components such as sugars, amino acids, and nucleotides. Dendrimers have a central core, an internal dendritic structure, and an exterior surface with functional groups. These components are used in a variety of ways to create products that protect internal cores in a range of sizes and forms. Gene transfection, medication delivery, catalysis, and energy harvesting are a few uses for dendrimers.

2.1.2.3 Polymersomes

These micelles are self-assembled and made of either natural or synthetic polymers. Polymersomes are highly stable and highly specific. The rate at which cancer cells from the mammary glands spread has decreased in mice when nanobodies are used [16]. Two surface antigens have been found to be expressed and active in 20% to 30% of cancer

cases: Human Epidermal Growth

2.1.3 Inorganic nanoparticles:

The central core of the majority of inorganic nanoparticles exhibits electrical, magnetic, and fluorescent properties. An organic protective layer covers their surface. As a result, the core cannot be reached by environmental degradation agents. However, these inorganic nanoparticles have the ability to form covalent or electrostatic bonds with positively charged molecules.

2.1.3.1 Quantum dots

Quantum dots are fluorescent nanoparticles with a central core that contains hundreds of atoms of group V (like indium), group III (like tantalum), group VI, and group II (like selenide, zinc, technetium, and cadmium) elements (10-2 nm). Cadmium selenide and zinc sulfide make up the core of quantum dots, which are encased in a layer of ligand and amphiphilic polymer. The use of quantum dots in in vivo medicinal and imaging applications is restricted due to the harmful effects of heavy metal cores.

2.1.3.2 Gold Nanoparticles

Breast cancer is diagnosed, imaged, and treated with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). These particles are used as medication carriers and contrast agents. A variety of peptides can be conjugated to AuNP to improve stability, selective targeting, and biocompatibility. There are multiple steps in the mechanism by which AuNPs work in the body. AuNPs first bind to their receptors. They then oscillate when exposed to light or radiofrequency pulses. Consequently, AuNPs release heat and absorb light. As a result, the cell's surroundings heat up. Consequently, there has been irreversible heat cellular damage.

2.1.3.3 Magnetic Nanoparticles

Noninvasive methods like MRI can detect magnetic nanoparticles. Superparamagnetic Iron Oxide Nanoparticles (SPIONs) and Monocrystalline Iron Oxide Nanoparticles (MION) are used in specific delivery of drugs. SPIONs are proper for increasing contrast and are

used in MRI. Magnetic nanoparticles with an outer coating of an organic substance are suitable for conjugating to biomolecules and can be used to carry drugs in the cancer treatment. Iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles are applied as a magnetic resonance agent for cell trafficking researches, angiogenesis and gene expression researches. Different conjugation of inorganic nanoparticles with different factors and their applications for cancer diagnosis and treatment are presented

2.2 AI in ovarian cancer detection

Machines can be trained to handle data more effectively through the application of machine learning (ML). Occasionally, we are unable to decipher the information extracted from the data after seeing it. We use machine learning in that scenario. The need for machine learning is growing as a result of the large number of datasets that are available. Machine learning is used in many industries to retrieve pertinent data. Learning from the data is the aim of machine learning. How to teach robots to learn without explicit programming has been the subject of numerous studies. Numerous mathematicians and programmers use a variety of methods to solve this problem, which involves large data sets.

Figure 3: Machine learning classification

Various algorithms are used in machine learning to address data issues.

2.2.1 Supervised learning

The machine learning task of supervised learning involves using sample input-output pairs to train a function that maps an input to an output. It uses labeled training data, which consists of a collection of training samples, to infer a function. The algorithms that require outside help are known as supervised machine learning algorithms. Train and test datasets are separated from the input dataset. The output variable in the train dataset requires

classification or prediction. Every algorithm. Discover some patterns in the training dataset and use them to predict or classify the test dataset. The figure below shows the supervised machine learning algorithms' workflow. Here, the most well-known supervised machine learning methods have been covered.

Figure 4 Supervised Learning Model

2.2.1.1 Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is another popular cutting-edge machine learning method. Support-vector machines in machine learning are supervised learning models that examine data for regression and classification using related learning methods. By implicitly mapping their inputs into high-dimensional feature spaces, a technique known as the kernel trick, SVMs can effectively do non-linear classification in addition to linear classification. In essence, it creates boundaries between the classes. The margins are created to minimize the classification error by creating the greatest possible space between the margin and the classes.

2.2.1.2 Decision Tree

A decision tree is a graph that shows options and their outcomes as a tree. The decision rules or conditions are represented by the graph's edges, while the nodes in the graph stand for an event or option. Every tree has branches and nodes. Each branch denotes a value that the node may accept, and each node indicates characteristics in a group that needs to be categorized.

2.2.1.3 Navie Bayes

It is a classification method predicated on the

independence of predictors and based on the Bayes Theorem. To put it simply, a Naive Bayes classifier makes the assumption that a feature's existence in a class has nothing to do with the existence of any other features. The text categorization industry is the primary aim of Naïve Bayes. It is mostly used for classification and clustering, depending on the conditional likelihood of occurrence.

2.2.2 Unsupervised Learning:

These are referred to as unsupervised learning since, in contrast to the supervised learning described above, there are no teacher or right answers. It is up to the algorithms to find and display the intriguing structure in the data. Few features are learned from the data by the unsupervised learning algorithms. It recognizes the data's class when new data is introduced by using the previously learned features. Clustering and feature reduction are its primary applications.

Figure 5 Unsupervised Learning Model

2.2.2.1 K-Means Clustering

One of the most straightforward unsupervised learning algorithms for resolving the well-known clustering problem is K-means. The process uses a set number of clusters to categorize a given data set in a straightforward and easy way. Establishing k centers—one for each cluster—is the key concept. These centers should be strategically positioned because different locations yield varied outcomes. Therefore, it is preferable to position them as far apart as feasible.

2.2.2.2 Principal Component Analysis

A statistical process known as principal component analysis transforms a collection of observations of potentially correlated variables into a set of values of linearly uncorrelated variables known as principal components using an orthogonal transformation. This reduces the data's dimension

to facilitate and speed up computations. It uses linear combinations to explain a set of variables' variance-covariance structure. It is frequently employed as a method for reducing dimensionality.

Figure 6 PCA Model

2.2.3 Semi Supervise Learning:

Combining supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques results in semi-supervised machine learning. It can be useful in machine learning and data mining applications if unlabeled data is already available and obtaining labeled data is a laborious procedure. More popular supervised machine learning techniques involve using a "labeled" dataset, where each record contains the result information, to train a machine learning algorithm. Below is a discussion of a few semi-supervised learning algorithms.

2.2.3.1 Transductive SVM

In semisupervised learning, transductive support vector machines (TSVM) have been utilized extensively to handle partially labeled data. Due to a lack of knowledge regarding its generalization-based core, there has been uncertainty around it. In order to maximize the margin between the labeled and unlabeled data, it is utilized to label the unlabeled data.

2.2.3.2 Generative Models

A generative model is one that has the ability to produce data. It models the class (i.e., the entire data) as well as the features. All algorithms that model $P(x,y)$ are generative since I can create data

points using this probability distribution if we model $P(x,y)$. For each component, one labeled example is sufficient to verify the distribution of the mixture.

2.2.3.3 Self-Training

A classifier is learned using a subset of labeled data in self-training. After that, unlabeled data is given into the classifier. The training set is the sum of the unlabeled points and the expected labels. This process is then carried out once more. Self-training gets its name from the fact that the classifier is learning itself.

2.2.3.4 Reinforcement Learning

The field of machine learning known as reinforcement learning studies how software agents should behave in a given setting to optimize a concept of cumulative reward. Along with supervised and unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning is one of the three fundamental machine learning paradigms.

2.2.3.5 Multitask Learning

By utilizing the similarities between several tasks, multi-task learning, a branch of machine learning, seeks to solve numerous tasks simultaneously. This can serve as a regularizer and increase learning efficiency. Formally, Multi-Task Learning (MTL) will improve the learning of a particular model by using the knowledge contained in all n tasks. This is applicable if there are n tasks (conventional deep learning approaches aim to solve just 1 task using 1 particular model), and these n tasks or a subset of them are related to each other but not exactly identical.

2.2.3.6 Ensemble Learning

The act of systematically generating and combining several models, such as classifiers or experts, to address a specific computational intelligence challenge is known as ensemble learning. The main purpose of ensemble learning is to enhance a model's performance or lessen the possibility of selecting a bad model by accident. Additional uses for ensemble learning include error-correction, data

fusion, incremental learning, non-stationary learning, choosing optimal features, and giving a confidence level to the model's choice.

2.2.3.7 Boosting:

A class of algorithms known as "boosting" is used to transform poor learners into strong ones. One method for reducing bias and variation in ensemble learning is called "boosting."

2.2.3.8 Bagging

When a machine learning algorithm's accuracy and stability need to be improved, bagging or bootstrap aggregating is used. It can be used in regression and classification. Additionally, bagging reduces variance and facilitates the management of overfitting.

Conclusion

Both supervised and unsupervised machine learning are possible. Choose supervised learning if you have less data and training data that is clearly labeled. Large data sets would often yield higher performance and outcomes from unsupervised learning. Use deep learning techniques if you have a large data collection at your fingertips. Reinforcement learning and deep reinforcement learning have also been taught to you. You now understand the definition, uses, and constraints of neural networks. Several machine learning algorithms are reviewed in this study. Nowadays, machine learning is used by everyone, whether they are aware of it or not. An overview of the majority of the widely used machine learning algorithms is provided in this work.

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